

Formation of Al_5Te_4 in Solid State and its Characterisation

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Al_5Te_4 , prepared by heat-treatment of the constituent elements, has a cubic unit cell dimension with $a=6.147 \text{ \AA}$. Differential scanning calorimetry suggests that the telluride undergoes a reversible phase transformation in the temperature range 707–729.7 K. The material is diamagnetic in nature. Kinetic analysis under dynamic conditions shows that the transformation process is associated with high value of entropy of activation, which suggests that the transition state in the process is highly disordered. Isothermal data follow the Mampel unimolecular law of random nucleation.

METAL chalcogenides form an interesting class of materials, which exhibit wide variety of properties¹. Formation of a number of aluminium tellurides, which fall in this category of materials, is reported in literature². However, less is known about their characterisation. In the present investigation, formation of Al_5Te_4 , its crystal structure and behaviour on thermal treatment (differential scanning calorimetry and thermogravimetry) are reported. Magnetic susceptibility, as a function of temperature, has been measured in the temperature range 323–733 K. From the DSC data, kinetic parameters have been computed.

Experimental

Small aluminium pieces cut from the metal foil (A.R.) and tellurium powder (A.R.) were mixed in 5 : 4 ratio, vacuum sealed in silica ampules and heat-treated at 873 K for 96 h with two intermediate grindings. The final product was crushed to fine powder of the size below 74μ . The product was chemically analysed for Al and Te by the usual methods³.

X-Ray diffraction studies : X-Ray powder diffraction of the product was recorded on a Phillips PW 1050/70 diffractometer at a scanning speed of $1^\circ/\text{min}$ using $\text{CuK}\alpha$ radiation ($\lambda = 1.5418 \text{ \AA}$). The diffraction data were indexed to find the cell parameters. The experimental X-ray diffraction data and the computed data are given in Table 1.

Thermal analysis : Differential scanning calorimetric curve (dH/dt vs T) of the sample (2.819 g) was recorded on a Mettler TA 3000 thermal analysis system in a continuous flow of nitrogen (30 ml min^{-1}) at a scanning speed of 10 K/min , and cooling curve of the sample was also recorded under similar conditions (Fig. 1). To understand the mechanism of the reaction, α (fraction of the reaction completed) vs t (time) plots were recorded by the DSC at three different temperatures (Fig. 2). To ascertain

TABLE 1—X-RAY DIFFRACTION DATA FOR Al_5Te_4

hkl	I/I_0	d_{exp} $\text{\AA}$	d_{cal} $\text{\AA}$
211	15	2.521	2.510
300	100	2.040	2.049
331	30	1.419	1.410
421	19	1.341	1.341
422	8	1.252	1.262
333	6	1.182	1.183
440	13	1.091	1.087
441	8	1.073	1.070
542	5	0.913	0.916
631	4	0.903	0.906
444	3	0.884	0.887
550	4	0.868	0.869
552	4	0.838	0.837

Unit cell dimension, $a=6.147 \text{ \AA}$.

any mass change in the temperature range 323–773 K, the sample was subjected to thermogravimetric analysis in nitrogen atmosphere at a scanning speed of 10 K/min .

Magnetic susceptibility : Magnetic susceptibility of the sample was recorded on a Gouy magnetic balance at 323–723 K at a constant magnetic field of 3000 gauss using $\text{HgCo}(\text{CNS})_4$ as calibrant.

Hot-stage microscopy : The sample was observed under a locally fabricated hot-stage, provided with a metallurgical microscope, in the temperature range 323–773 K under continuous flow of nitrogen and found that the sample remained in the solid state in this temperature range.

Results and Discussion

The elemental analysis suggested that Al and Te were present to the extent of 23 and 77%, respectively. This gives the stoichiometry of the sample as Al_5Te_4 . The X-ray diffraction data could be indexed for a unit cubic cell with $a=6.147 \text{ \AA}$.

The DSC curve (Fig. 1a) shows an endothermic transition at 707–729.7 K, with peak temperature of 719.4 K. The enthalpy change associated with the transition is 84 J g^{-1} . The cooling curve (Fig. 1b) exhibits an exothermic transition at 495–523 K, with peak temperature of 510 K. The cooling curve and the rerun curve show that the transformation

Fig. 1. (a) Heating DSC curve (dH/dt vs T) and (b) cooling DSC curve for Al_5Te_4 .

process is reversible. The cooling curve shows that the transition is associated with unusually very high thermal hysteresis (209 K). Thermogravimetry suggests that no mass loss is associated with the transformation. The results show that Al_5Te_4 undergoes a reversible phase transformation. The thermal hysteresis observed in the transformation process suggests that the two phases co-exist over a wide range of temperature and the thermal equilibrium is not established in this temperature range.

The magnetic measurements suggest that the material is diamagnetic in character ($\chi_m = -90 \times 10^{-6}$ cgs units mol^{-1}).

Kinetic analysis: Generally, kinetic parameters from the DSC data are computed on the basis of the equation (1)⁴,

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = A e^{-E/RT} (1-\alpha)^n \quad (1)$$

Assuming that the heat evolved or absorbed by the system during the transformation at any time t is proportional to the number of moles of the reactant consumed, the above equation in the logarithmic form is transformed to

$$\ln \frac{dH/dt}{H_t} = \ln A - E/RT + n \ln H_t/H_i \quad (2)$$

where, dH/dt is the rate of heat flow, H_i the total enthalpy of the reaction (total peak area) and H_t the remaining area of the DSC peak. From the DSC measurements, dH/dt , H_i , T and H_t are known ;

consequently, rest of the parameters can be calculated. Based on this principle, $\ln A$ and E have been calculated for the transformation with the aid of a programme available in the microprocessor TC 10, provided with the Mettler thermal analysis system.

From the energy of activation and specific reaction rate at any given temperature, the entropy of activation ($\Delta S^\ddagger$) for the activation process has been calculated using the relationship⁵,

$$\Delta S^\ddagger = \frac{\Delta H^\ddagger}{T} + R \ln \frac{k'h}{kT} \quad (3)$$

where, $\Delta H^\ddagger = E - RT$ (for a solid state reaction), k' is the specific reaction rate and k the Boltzmann constant. The value of $\Delta S^\ddagger$ comes out to be 2.71 kJ mol^{-1} . In view of the narrow range of transition temperature, the transformation is of the first order. Such sharp transformations will lead to high value of the entropy of activation, which is true in this case. However, because of strong correlation between $\ln A$ and E , 95% confidence limits are large (58 and 350 for $\ln A$ and E , respectively), resulting in high degree of uncertainty in the values of the kinetic parameters. The absolute values of the parameters under dynamic conditions are only indicative of the nature of the process. Fairly large value of the entropy of activation suggests that the transition state in the transformation process is highly disordered. This would result in high value of the partition function for the activated state, which leads to high value of the pre-exponential factor. This is the reason that very high value of the pre-exponential factor ($\ln A = 678$) has been observed in this case.

To understand the mechanism of the phase transformation, various kinetic equations applicable to solid state reactions under different mechanisms were applied to the isothermal kinetic data. It has been observed that the isothermal data given in Fig. 2 follow the Mampel unimolecular law of random nucleation⁶,

$$kt = -\ln(1-\alpha) \quad (4)$$

Fig. 2. Plots of α vs t for the phase transformation.

The applicability of equation (4) is shown in Fig. 3. Plots of $-\ln \ln 1/(1-\alpha)$ vs $\ln t$ are linear with slope

of the order of unity. The energy of activation has been calculated for the isothermal process from the Arrhenius plot and comes out to be 381 kJ mol⁻¹. The applicability of the equation suggests that random nucleation of the product phase determines the reaction rate.

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Fig. 3. Plots of $\ln \ln 1/(1-x)$ vs $\ln t$.